

TRITERPENOIDS. PART VIII. TRITERPENES FROM THE BARK OF
ERVATAMIA CORONARIA STAPF.

By S. PATTABI RAMAN¹ AND A. K. BARUA

The stem-bark of *Ervatamia coronaria* has been found to contain (i) α -amyrin and its acetate, (ii) lupeol and its acetate and (iii) β -sitosterol.

Ervatamia coronaria Stapf. (syn. *Tabernaemontana coronaria* R. Br.) is a common garden plant belonging to the family of Apocyanaceae. Several parts of the plant are used in indigenous system of medicine (Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. II, p. 1577). From the bark of *E. coronaria*, Ratnagiriswaran and Venkatachalam (*Quart. J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1939, 12, 174) isolated a crystalline substance (m.p. 180-81°) with properties resembling those of a resin alcohol, and also two pharmacologically active alkaloids, named tabernaemontanine (m.p. 208-10°) and coronarine (m.p. 196-98°). Wari and Ahmed (*Pakistan J. Sci.*, 1949, 7, 128) also reported the presence of tabernaemontanine and a crystalline resin alcohol (m. p. 185-87°) which was not fully characterised.

It appeared of interest to us to investigate the bark of this plant. From the petroleum ether extract we have isolated the triterpene alcohols, α -amyrin and lupeol along with their acetates and also a sterol mixture from which β -sitosterol could be obtained in a pure state, and identified. The occurrence of the above triterpene alcohols as their acetates in nature is not very uncommon and has been reported as early as 1912 by Ultee (*Chem. Weekbl.*, 1912, 9, 773).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Air-dried powdered bark (1 kg.) was exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). Removal of the solvent left a light yellow viscous mass which was taken up in the minimum volume of benzene and adsorbed on a column of Brockmann alumina (50 cm × 2 cm). The column was then eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°, 1.5 litres), petroleum ether-benzene mixture (1:1, 300 c.c.), benzene (500 c.c.) and finally with chloroform (500 c.c.). The petroleum ether eluate, on crystallisation from chloroform-methanol mixture, gave an almost white amorphous mass, m.p. 138-82° (5.8 g., Fraction A). The petroleum ether-benzene and benzene eluates gave only very small amounts of gummy residues. The chloroform fraction, on crystallisation from chloroform-methanol mixture and subsequently from aqueous ethanol, yielded colorless crystalline flakes, m.p. 115-30° (0.9 g., Fraction B).

Fraction A was dissolved in minimum volume of benzene and adsorbed on a column of active alumina (48 cm × 2 cm). The column was then eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°, 600 c.c.), and 25 c.c. portions were collected successively.

From the different fractions solid residues were obtained which had melting point ranges from 156°-185°. These solids were mixed up and crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, when two fractions having m.p. 185-95° (Fraction C) and m.p. 198-210° (Fraction D) respectively were obtained. The column was then successively eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) - benzene mixture (1:1, 600 c.c.) and chloroform (300 c.c.). Both these eluates furnished white crystalline residues having m.p. 142-59°. On repeated crystallisations from aqueous ethanol, the m.p. rose to 156-63° (0.6 g., Fraction E).

Fraction C was rechromatographed over active alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) as the eluent and the residue from the eluate was repeatedly crystallised from chloroform-methanol mixture, when shining leaflets, m.p. 211-22°, $[\alpha]_D + 79^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), were obtained. (Found: C, 81.69; H, 11.25. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.12%). It did not depress the melting point of an authentic sample of α -amyrin acetate. The substance was hydrolysed with alcoholic caustic potash and on crystallisation of the product from aqueous alcohol gave long needles, m.p. 185-86°, which depressed the m.p. of the parent substance but not that of a sample of α -amyrin. Found: C, 84.31; H, 11.9. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%. The above hydrolysis product yielded, on benzylation by the usual method, a benzoate, m.p. 197-98°, which did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of α -amyrin benzoate. (Found: C, 83.65; H, 10.4. Calc. for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 83.7; H, 10.3%).

Fraction D, on rechromatography over alumina and repeated crystallisations from chloroform-methanol mixture, gave needles, m.p. 213-15°, $[\alpha]_D + 47^\circ.5$ (in CHCl_3) whose identity with lupeol acetate was established by a direct comparison of the m.p. and mixed m.p. (Found: C, 81.8; H, 10.99. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 81.99; H, 11.12%). The substance could be hydrolysed to yield a product crystallising as needles from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 211-12°, which depressed the m.p. of the parent compound but the m.p. remained unchanged when mixed with lupeol. (Found: C, 84.29; H, 11.92. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.44; H, 11.81%). The benzoate of this product formed colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 261-62°, which were identified as those of lupeol benzoate by comparison of the mixed m.p. (Found: C, 83.59; H, 10.5. Calc. for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 83.7; H, 10.3%).

Fraction E was rechromatographed over alumina but there was not much improvement in the melting point. It was benzylated and the product, on chromatographic resolution and crystallisation from ether-methanol mixture, gave two compounds, m.p. 196-97° and 262-64°, which were found to be identical with α -amyrin benzoate and lupeol benzoate respectively, by comparison of the mixed melting points. The individual benzoates furnished on hydrolysis the corresponding alcohols. Thus *Fraction E* is proved to be a mixture of the free triterpene alcohols-lupeol and α -amyrin.

Fraction B was directly acetylated and the product on chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina and crystallisation from aqueous ethanol gave a compound, m.p. 126-27°, $[\alpha]_D - 41^\circ.5$ and another compound, m.p. 136-38°, in low yield. The latter could be hydrolysed to a substance, m.p. 141-48°, but the yield was too low for

further study. The former compound did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample of β -sitosterol acetate. (Found: C, 81.42; H, 11.5. Calc. for $C_{31}H_{52}O_2$: C, 81.52; H, 11.44%). This on hydrolysis gave β -sitosterol, m.p. 136-37°, the identity of which was established by the mixed melting point method. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 12.2. Calc. for $C_{29}H_{48}O$: C, 83.99; H, 12.15%). It also gave a benzoate, m.p. 144-45°. (Found: C, 83.24; H, 10.5. Calc. for $C_{38}H_{56}O_2$: C, 83.34; H 10.49%).

Further investigation of the bark is under progress.

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BOSE RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
CALCUTTA.

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